

SURVEILLANCE CARD_ Hepatitis E_Pathogen detection in pigs breeding stock

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Pathogen detection in pigs breeding stock.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of a change in the geographic distribution/spread to new herds or production units. Target for surveillance: farms with greater probability of consequences for the pig production chain if infected.
3	Target species and group	Sock samples can be used to sample whole pens/units. Alternatively, pooled fecal samples can be used, focusing on weaner pigs before moving to the fattening unit.
4	Target sector / production type	Nucleus and multiplier breeding herds, and all other herds that move/sell weaners or rearing pigs in relevant quantities.
5	Geographical area covered	Whole country.
6	Age group	Weaner pigs, or pigs older than 8 -10 weeks (see "Target species and group").
7	Sampling point and strategy	Sampling on farm with targeted sampling of animal groups to be moved. Sock samples are used to sample a pen/animal group. Alternatively, faecal matter will be sampled randomly.
8	Sampling time period	Year-round / not limited.
9	Sampling matrix	Pooled faecal samples or sock samples (1; 2).
10	Type of disease indicators	Antigen detection (viral RNA).
11	Sampling unit	a pen/pig group / 1 sock sample for all pens of a batch of pigs/ Pooled sample of 10 feces per pen (1).
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Pigs from farms with a HEV-negative history, but at risk of HEV introduction, and pigs from farms with unknown HEV-status. Within the farm, animals housed together in the same pen form a group.

13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Identification of the agent through (real-time) RT-PCR on pooled faecal matter. Positive samples can be sequenced using Sanger sequencing or comparable methods.
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	To be defined and reported.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	To be defined and reported, ideally 95%.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	The focus is on herds with higher probability of spreading, rather than higher risk of infection. With a proper sampling design to ensure representativeness, the sensitivity of the component can be calculated, and used to estimate an overall sensitivity of the system combined with other components.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	<i>Cryptosporidia</i> spp., <i>Giardia</i> spp. and a broad range of intestinal pathogens in pig herds. As on-farm sampling is required for this surveillance component, parallel sampling of other matrices could be considered to target more pathogens.
18	References	<p>1) Pedersen KS, Okholm E, Johansen M, Angen Ø, Jorsal SE, Nielsen JP and Bækbo P, 2015. Clinical utility and performance of sock sampling in weaner pig diarrhoea. <i>Preventive Veterinary Medicine</i>, 120(3-4), 313 – 320. doi: 10.1016/j.prevetmed.2015.04.015.</p> <p>2) Lienhard J, Vonlanthen-Specker I, Sidler X and Bachofen C, 2021. Screening of Swiss Pig Herds for Hepatitis E Virus: A Pilot Study. <i>Animals</i>, 11(11), 3050. doi: 10.3390/ani11113050.</p> <p>3) Meester M, Bouwknecht M, Hakze-van der Honing R, Vernooij H, Houben M, van Oort S, van der Poel WHM, Stegeman A and Tobias T, 2022. Repeated cross-sectional sampling of pigs at slaughter indicates varying age of hepatitis E virus infection within and between pig farms. <i>Veterinary Research</i>, 53, 50. doi.org/10.1186/s13567-022-01068-3.</p>